

THE DEMOGRAPHIC DECLINE IN ȚINUTUL PĂDURENILOR - ANALYZING THE FIRST QUARTER OF THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

The purpose of this scientific endeavor is to raise awareness of the current situation regarding Ținutul Pădurenilor (Ținutul Pădurenilor, as it has been presented on the international promotional website). It is an ethnographic area of great importance to the entirety of the Romanian mountain area, being investigated for centuries. The present paper presents some specific elements of the ethnographic area, using available bibliography written by a series of researchers. Then, using the cartographic method, the communes, and composing villages are presented. Through the investigation technique, there has been organized a series of interviews with members of the local population, to show the current situation and present dysfunctions. Ținutul Pădurenilor and likewise, the whole of the Romanian mountain area needs improvements that have to manifest through complex interventions and recovery strategies of the padurean space.

Keywords: Ținut, Pădureni, Poiana Ruscă, ethnography, decline

INTRODUCTION

The different ethnographic spaces that dot the map of Romania have always represented fundamental elements for the Romanian society. They have contributed, firstly, by conserving elements of the material and immaterial heritage, by solidifying certain communities that are characterized by distinct elements in regards to neighboring communities, all while keeping at a national level the Romanian identity.

The geographic literature talks about a genuine *mental ethnographic space*. This means a space that people can associate with elements such as traditional clothing, customs, tradition, way of thinking and that they clearly distinguish from other humanized spaces.

The pădureni of Hunedoara (pădurean = one who resides in or near a forested area) are those who reside in the villages situated on the eastern slope of Poiana Ruscă Mountains, between the Cerna valley and the Mures valley. The area inhabited by them, surrounded by forests, is known as Ținutul Pădurenilor (en: Land of the Pădureni) and is situated West of the municipality of Hunedoara. The interest in researching the pădureni and the area existed for the last few centuries.

Romulus Vuia considered it an "ethnographic wonder". SECOȘAN (1984) considered that, at least from a clothing and craftsmanship point of view, Ținutul Pădurenilor is a unique treasure, a living and breathing archive of documents.

From a structural point of view, the villages of Ținutul Pădurenilor have a compact structure. In general, villages in mountain areas have a more dispersed structure (SURD, 2004, pp. 28-29), however, this particularity in the western Hunedoara space is imposed by the relief. So, the villages are situated mostly on hilltops and mountaintops (the valley villages are the exceptions to the rule). Geology and geomorphology themselves dictated the placing of villages at a high elevation. The multiple abrupts, the steep slopes and the massiveness of the relief

impose an inverse structure of the agricultural activities (the normal being as follows: villages form in the valleys, and as altitude increases, forests and alpine meadows follow). In the case of the pǎdureni, valleys have a reduced extent, the slopes are forested and improper for settlements, while villages organize around hilltops and mountaintops in order to fully exploit the agricultural terrains on the neighboring plateaus.

Fig. 1. Ținutul Pǎdurenilor from a county and national territorial perspective

Also due to the diversity and arrangement of the relief, the population density is small and unequal. Although ILINCA proposes for the Western Romanian Carpathians (Poiana Ruscă being a component) a density of 41.38 people/sq km (ILINCA, 2012, p.49), this number is much lower in Poiana Ruscă Mountains. In addition to the low population, the villages are assembled in a disparate pattern.

IȘFĂNONI (2004) considered, taking into account three villages (Goleș, Alun and Vadu Dobrii), that, in regards to depopulation, they have a few common traits: 1) high elevations and position of the village built-up area on a mountaintop; 2) mountain road network, poorly maintained; 3) poor means of worker transportation; 4) low Natural Growth Rate; 5) gradual closing of schools because of reduction in the number of born children; 6) the risk of being moved to lowland areas by the socialist authorities (this determined the pǎdureni to move their families to destinations of choice, rather than an imposed destination)

Through this short analysis, we've aimed to emphasize the demographic decline in Ținutul Pǎdurenilor, a decline specific to the entirety of the Romanian mountain area. There has been an attempt of interviewing a few members of the pǎdureni community, to observe the depopulation phenomenon, as it presents itself from inside the community. The hypothesis is that Ținutul Pǎdurenilor undergoes a degradation process in every domain, but most importantly from an economic and social point of view, and there is a need for it to be subjected to a complex recovery strategy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is necessary to mention the communes and villages considered components of the pădureni ethnographic area. Romulus Vuia included the villages of Strigoanea, Stăncești, Ohaba, Rădulești and Făgețel in Ținutul Pădurenilor. IȘFĂNONI (2004) excludes them due to not finding concrete material evidence after research in these villages (their traditional costumes bear resemblance to the Mures Valley costumes). Cartographic materials have been developed using ArcGIS 10.6, to better observe the analyzed territorial context.

Fig. 2. Villages (white dots) and communes that form the ethnographic area (Romulus Vuia's 20th-century research)

For the cartographic support, databases regarding relief, administrative-territorial units, and hydrography have been used. This way, there can be immediately observed that most villages don't reside along important watercourses or in valleys, but rather on elevated points.

Therefore, when talking about pădureni villages, the communes we refer to are:

- A. Communes where every village is part of the ethnographic space: Ghelari (4 villages), Bunila (5 villages), Lelese (4 villages), Cerbăl (8 villages) and Bătrâna (4 villages)
- B. Communes where only certain villages are part of Ținutul Pădurenilor
 - a) Toplița: Administrates 8 villages, but only 4 are of interest: Dăbâca, Goleș, Hășdău and Văləri
 - b) Peștișu Mic: Administrates 9 villages, but only 2 are relevant: Ciulpăz and Cutin
 - c) Vețel: Administrates 10 villages, but only 4 are part of the ethnographic area: Muncelu Mare, Muncelu Mic, Runcu Mic and Boia Bârzii
 - d) Dobra: Administrates 13 villages, but only 4 can be included in Ținutul Pădurenilor: Făgețel, Rădulești, Stăncești-Ohaba and Stăncești. For some contemporary authors, these are not components of Ținutul Pădurenilor, because they bear similarities to the Mures Valley space, not

the pădureni space. Romulus Vuia, one of the most prominent researchers in this field of the 20th century, included them as well.

Fig. 3. Villages (white dots) and communes included in the ethnographic area by late 20th century researchers and contemporary ones, including Ișfănoni R. (Dobra excluded)

In addition, to better analyze the demographic situation of this mountain area, graphic materials have been realized using Microsoft Excel (Office 365 edition). For the year 2002, the national census database has been consulted at a village and commune level (source: kia.hu). One of the limits of the research was that it was not possible to observe the demographic evolution at a village level for the 2011 national census.

That is the reason why, for the first graph (Fig. 3.), the data used was the demographic evolution at a commune level for the years 2002 and 2011. For the record, in the case of this graph, all the population from the communes was taken into consideration, from pădureni villages and other villages alike.

For the second graph (Fig. 4.), the data from (kia.hu) has been used, regarding the years 1992 and 2002. This data was used because, at a village level, there is no data level for the 2011 national census, only for prior censuses. It has been an attempt to emphasize the demographic tendency exclusively for the Ținutul Pădurenilor area, meaning only certain villages from 4 communes. And so, even though the graph says the name of the commune, in reality only the population of relevant villages have been added.

Out of the 9 communes, 8 registered a significant population decline: Ghelari, Toplița, Bunila, Lelese, Cerbăl, Peștișu Mic, Bătrâna. Dobra commune registered, during 2002-2011, a decrease from 3499 people to 3345, meaning a decrease of 154 residents, even though it's in the vicinity of a major road and the relief is more permissive. Vetel commune is in a similar context to Dobra but registered an increase from 2760 people in 2002 to 2872 in 2011.

Fig. 4. General demographic evolution for all communes that include pădureni villages (source: National Statistic Institution)

Fig. 5. Demographic evolution at a village level only for the pădureni villages in mixed communes (source: kia.hu)

There has been no field research, this representing a weak point of the entire research. However, three members of the pădureni community have been interviewed, to offer their perspective regarding the situation of their community. The starting premise before the interviews was that the area has economic and tourist potential, but is in an economic and

demographic decline. All three respondents are employees in economic units based in the municipality of Hunedoara. The questions that they were addressed, in a language close to the day-by-day vocabulary, focused on their origin, the economic situation, the demographic situation, the occupational structure, existing investments, flux of tourists and the seasonal flux of the local population. The supposition that was analyzed was that the pādureni, like other Romanians from all over the country, return to their home places during the warm season or during vacation/holidays. The last question referred to the current situation of the Pādureni Festival at Poienița Voinii, an event that for many years attracted tourists and pādureni alike.

The interviews were done with the participation of three members from the local community. They hail from 2 mountaintop villages (Vălari and Cernișoara Florese) and one valley village (Hășdău). The municipality of Hunedoara economically polarizes these villages, especially because of the small distance and possibilities of public transportation. Further, we will mention only the most essential aspects of the interview. The questions addressed by the interviewer will be noted using italic, and the text without any format will be the information offered by the respondents, brought to a more synthetic form. The information given by them was processed using synonyms and expressions closer to the scientific sphere. The anonymity of the respondents will be kept and only their home village name will be used.

Respondent #1: Cernișoara Florese village. *What is the economic activity of the villagers?* A: In general they work in agriculture, namely animal raising, sheep and cattle. They work in the wood industry as well, exploiting the local forests. *Is the population number constant or in decline?* A: It's declining, but there are still people left. During summer, some people who left return to Florese and Alun villages. During the first days of August, the Festival at Poienița Voinii takes place. *Did you notice any investment in the last years?* A: Other than two communal roads, Florese – Bunila and Florese – Vălari, I don't know about any other investment. *Is there tourism in your area?* A: Especially during the summer, occasional tourists appear and visit the Marble Quarry in Alun, and the village church (The Wooden Church in Cernișoara-Florese, that is not on the list of historical monuments, n.a.).

Respondent #2: Vălari village. *What is the economic activity of the villagers?* A: Mostly agriculture, animal raising, pigs especially. A neighbor accessed European funding to invest in a micro-farm. *Is the population number constant or in decline?* A: I don't know if it's increasing or decreasing, but most have city residences. Most return to the village during weekends. The older folks are amongst the only ones who permanently live in the village. *Did you notice any investment in the last years?* A: Something was done concerning the transport infrastructure, the main village road. There has been some investment in the Cultural House of the village. *Is there tourism in your area?* A: During summer I see tourists, especially bikers. They come to see the Wooden Church in our village, which is a historical monument (it was dated using the dendrochronological method to 1677, and is listed as a II-B historical monument, of county importance, n.a.). Tourists also come to see the Pādureni Festival, but since Drăgan Muntean died (artist from Ținutul Pădurenilor, who became a symbol/local emblem, n.a.), most participants are locals.

Respondent #3: Hășdău village. *What is the economic activity of the villagers?* A: A lot of them left for the city, and if they live in the village, many benefit from social aid. A small number of families, 4-5 at most out of all the commune population, as far as I know, managed to create farms financed with European funds. The number of animals declined significantly (cattle and sheep). *Is the population number constant or in decline?* A: I think it's declining. Anyway, most people return to the village during holidays, especially Easter or Christmas. *Did you notice*

any investment in the last years? A: The roads and alleys were paved with asphalt. We don't have tap water, sewage, internet cables. We have satellite signal from a few phone networks. *Are there traditional crafts still practiced?* A: No, at least, the women don't anymore, they don't sew carpets or blankets, and so on. *Is there tourism in your area?* Tourists come but from small distances. During summer I see bicyclists from Hunedoara who stroll around these parts. Sometimes people come to relax upstream from the village, in the direction of Vadu Dobrii, where the scenery is more picturesque, but they're still mostly locals. The festival isn't so popular lately, the artists are fewer, and only from around these parts.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The first socio-economic changes that led to the destabilization of the ethnographic society started in the fifth decade of the last century. Then, mostly in the economic sphere, "a process of Fordist industrialization takes place (50-80 years after the apparition of this model) [...]. Engaged in pharaonic projects that surpass its capacity, Romania knows a continuous degradation of its socio-economic life" (PĂCURAR, p. 9). Industrialization is felt in Hunedoara county as well, the pādureni representing the most immediate workforce near the newly built furnaces of the Hunedoara Ironworks. In both Hunedoara and Ghelari, new schools appear destined to prepare workers, engineers, foremen, etc. Among the first families to leave the area and move to Hunedoara, was one family from Alun in 1953 (IȘFĂNONI, p.310). An extremely relevant situation of depopulation can be observed in the village of Muncelu Mic. In 10 years (1992-2002), 2 out of 3 people left the village, declining from 350 to 135 people. This quick depopulation was supported by the closing of the local mines. For a few decades, complex minerals (lead, zinc, copper, gold, silver) have been extracted, and, after 1990, the mines were closed.

Fig. 6. Typical landscape in Poiana Ruscă Mountains (Source: Personal Archive)

Every single village in Ținutul Pădurenilor registers demographic declines, as shown in the entirety of the graphic materials. This data is based on the national censuses of 2002 and 2011, and we have serious reasons to believe that, when the next national census happens, the same negative tendency will be showcased, if not a worse one. If Dobra and Vețel communes registered an increase in population (Vețel) or a less significant decrease (Dobra), we think the reason is not the Natural Growth Rate, but rather the urban-rural migration. Situated near the city of Deva and the European Road E673, this determined part of the urban population to settle in these communes. Moreover, the elevation is lower here, the slopes are less steep, and while talking about the other villages at higher elevations, that are less accessible (namely, the pădureni villages), we can see a demographic decline that is visible and is shared with the other villages from Ținutul Pădurenilor. From the statements of the three respondents, a few clear conclusions can be made: 1) Ținutul Pădurenilor aligns with the other rural mountain areas of Romania from a demographic point of view. It undergoes depopulation, many people returning to the villages only during moments of vacation or holidays. The Natural Growth rate is negative. The residents that are left are mostly old. Some of the villages face disappearance because the population is close to zero. 2) Investments in different areas are extremely few and mostly focus on the transport infrastructure, their absence contributing to the lag of the area in relation to the surrounding ones. 3) Tourism isn't promoted, although the tourist potential is highly present, natural and anthropogenic alike. A step in the right direction was taken with the creation of the presentation website (ȚinutulPădurenilor.eu). The festival doesn't have the polarization power of the past. 4) The traditional customs, along with the population, are slowly disappearing, and from an ethnographic point of view, the area is in danger.

Interventions need to happen from a county and local scale to preserve this ethnographic area. Considered a treasure for Romania, today it is facing multiple dysfunctionalities that threaten its existence. If promoted and economically sustained, this area could become an emblem of foremost importance for Hunedoara county and the Vest development region. In the context of contemporary problems, the entirety of the mountain area of Romania needs to be sustained with complex interventions, and Ținutul Pădurenilor, along with Poiana Ruscă Mountains, requires the same treatment.

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